

Investigations on the Interaction of Oxide-free Clay and Humic Acid

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The interaction of soil humus and clay mineral has been studied with oxide-free clay to investigate the influence of the free oxides found associated with soil on such clay-humus bonding. It is found that the free oxides of iron and aluminium might form a "bridge link" between humic acid and clay particles. Such a link, however, is not so strong as in case of metal ions, which are very effective in bringing about the interaction of clays and humic acid.

In previous communications, the interaction of soil humus and clay was studied from the measurement of the base-exchange capacity¹, adsorption², bacterial decomposition³, and viscosity⁴. In all cases a strong bonding between the two, leading to the formation of molecular complex, was observed. In the present communication, an attempt has been made to investigate the influence, if at all, of free oxides associated with clay on such clay-humus interaction.

The study of the role of "free oxides" in the interaction of clay and humus is of interest in view of the fact that these oxides are almost always present in soils. Sideri⁵ observed that the formation of one aggregate from anisotropic colloidal particles of clay was hindered by admixtures, such as oxides of Fe and Al. The elimination of these oxides from the surface of clay particles increases capability of these particles to aggregate. It has also been observed by Sideri⁵ that these oxides of Fe and Al have a positive influence on the binding of humus only when these are present in very small amounts. Jung⁶ showed some evidences of the formation of "bridge link" between humus and clays by the sesquioxides of Fe and Al. In the present investigation, the possible effect of sesquioxides has been studied by observing the formation of clay-humus complexes with 'clean clays', i.e., clays from which the free oxides have been removed, and comparing the results with original clay-humic acid mixtures.

EXPERIMENTAL

The "free oxides" from the clay fraction were removed by aluminium-oxalic acid method according to Marshall and Jeffries⁷. KI clay isolated from a coastal soil (Kakdip

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1. *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1960, **23**, 145.

2. *This Journal*, 1960, **37**, 793.

3. *Ibid.*, 1961, **38**, 737.

4. *Ibid.*, 1961, **38**, 909.

5. *Soil Sci.*, 1938, **46**, 129.

6. *Bodenk. Pflanzn.*, 1943, **32**, 325.

7. *Soil Sci. Soc. Amer. Proc.*, 1945, **10**, 397.

soil), which is predominantly illitic, was used for this purpose. The b. e. c. of this oxide-free KI clay was determined by pH titration with $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ solution and was found to be 43 m.e./100g. The value is little less than the b.e.c. of the original KI clay (46 m.e./100g.). The humic acid (SHm) was extracted from Siliguri soil from Darjeeling, West Bengal, by the usual method¹, b.e.c. value of which was found to be 450 m.e./100 g. by titration with $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ solution. These two fractions, viz., the oxide-free KI clay and crude humic acid (SHm), were then mixed in different proportions in presence of different cations. The mixtures were kept in Jena bottles for about a week with occasional shaking for complete reaction and then each was analysed. The interaction was studied both by pH-titration¹ and by analytical method². The results are recorded in Tables I and II and shown graphically in Figs. 1 and 2. From the pH-titration curves in Fig. 3, it can be seen that the buffering capacity, $\text{pH}/\Delta\text{b.e.c.}$, increases with the increase in proportion of humus. The pH of the inflection also increases with proportion of humus.

FIG. 1

TABLE I

B. e. c. of oxide-free KI clay and SHm mixtures.*

B.e.c. of SHm = 450 m.e./100 g.

B.e.c. of oxide-free KI clay = 43 m.e./100 g.

Humic acid; clay.	pH at inflection.	B. e. c. (in m. e./100 g.).		Diff.
		Calc.	Found.**	
1 : 5	8.3	111	109.0	2(3)**
1 : 10	8.2	80	75.0	5(5)
1 : 20	8.1	62	56.0	6(6)
1 : 40	8.0	53	44.5	8.5(11)
1 : 60	8.0	50	38.5	11.5(15.5)
1 : 80	7.8	48	35.0	13(18)

*KI clay=Illitic clay from Kakdwip soil. SHm=Humic acid from Siliguri soil.

**Figures in parentheses indicate values with the original clay-humic acid mixtures.¹

TABLE II

Amount of non-extractable humic acid from oxide-free KI clay—SHm mixture.

Ions present.	Ratio humic acid: clay.	Humic acid taken.	Humic acid in Na ₂ CO ₃ extract.	Humic acid combined.*	
H ⁺	1 : 10	0.09 g.	0.0747 g.	0.0153 g.	17(18)%
	1 : 20	0.06	0.0480	0.0120	20(20)
	1 : 40	0.04	0.0304	0.0096	24(25)
	1 : 60	0.02	0.0140	0.0080	30(32)
Ca ²⁺	1 : 10	0.09	0.0684	0.0216	24(25)
	1 : 20	0.06	0.0420	0.0180	30(31)
	1 : 40	0.04	0.0260	0.0140	35(37)
	1 : 60	0.02	0.0120	0.0080	40(42)
Mg ²⁺	1 : 10	0.09	0.0630	0.0270	30(30)
	1 : 20	0.06	0.0384	0.0216	36(37)
	1 : 40	0.04	0.0220	0.0180	45(43)
	1 : 60	0.02	0.0104	0.0096	48(48)
Al ³⁺	1 : 10	0.09	0.0630	0.0270	30(30)
	1 : 20	0.06	0.0378	0.0222	37(36)
	1 : 40	0.04	0.0220	0.0180	45(44)
	1 : 60	0.02	0.0100	0.0100	50(48)
Fe ³⁺	1 : 10	0.09	0.0620	0.0280	31(32)
	1 : 20	0.06	0.0360	0.0240	40(38)
	1 : 40	0.04	0.0216	0.0184	46(46)
	1 : 60	0.02	0.0100	0.0100	50(50)

* Figures in parentheses indicate values with original clay-humic acid mixtures².

DISCUSSION

From the results cited in Tables I and II, it can be pointed out that the decrease of b. e. c. of KI clay-humic acid mixtures is little less, when the clay is 'clean', than the original clay-humic acid mixture. But such a difference has not been observed in the case of adsorption of humic acid by clay minerals. The amount of non-extractable humic acid by Na₂CO₃ solution from the clay-humus complex practically remains the same as in the original clay-humic acid mixture. So, it may be suggested that free oxides of Fe and Al might form a "bridge link" between humic acid and clay particles, as was considered by Jung⁵, thus facilitating to some extent the combination of these two components in soil. But such a link is not likely to be very strong as it cannot resist the Na₂CO₃-extraction. The co-ordination of -OH and -COOH groups of humic acid with the exchangeable metal or H⁺ ions present in clay is a much stronger linkage. Thus, whereas the oxides of Al and Fe are almost ineffective, the ions, Al³⁺ and Fe³⁺, take a considerable part in forming the clay-humus complexes. In soil most of the free oxides are in the gel state and hence their inactivity or lack of activity is understood. It is, however, likely

that in the colloidal condition, in which these oxides or their hydrated forms may be positively charged, mutual coagulation with the negatively charged clays and humic acid is possible. In that case they would act more or less like the metal ions, which, as we have seen, are very effective in bringing about the reaction between clays and humic acid.

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

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